

ISic0608

I.Sicily inscription 0608

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Phorbantia, Aegates Islands

Place of origin (modern)

Levanzo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Levanzo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR147266

1. D (is) M (anibus) s (acrum) .
2. Narcissus
3. vixit ann (is) $\overline{\text{III}}$
4. dieb (us) XXVIII
5. Thallus et
6. Pannychis
7. filio dulcis
8. ş,imo fecer (unt)
9. s (it) t (ibi) t (erra) l (evis) .

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491873

EDR 147266

EDCS 22100612

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7493 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

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